

5th Generation connected and automated mobility cross-border EU trials

D6.5 Information package for external SMEs to facilitate the design of new CAM applications v1.0

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Abbreviation / Term	Description
AR	Augmented Reality
CAM	Connected and Automated Mobility
CNF	Cloud Native Network Function
LMT	Latvian Mobile Telecommunications
NSA	Non-Stand Alone
OBU	On Board Unit
RSU	Road Side Unit
SA	Standalone
VNF	Virtual Network Function
VRU	Vulnerable Road Users

1 Executive Summary

The goal of this deliverable is to provide information to third party SMEs to join the project during the field trials and bring equipment and/or innovative services to be tested during the terrestrial and maritime trials. Therefore, the scope of the deliverable is centered in two main objectives: the first one is to provide enough information to third party SMEs about the 5G-ROUTES architecture, the place of the field trials and the intended use cases to be executed by the project partners and the second objective is to provide to the external SMEs enough information about the procedure that will be followed to apply and evaluate the applications received from the SMEs. The participation of the external SMEs in the project is important since they can bring innovative Connected and Automated Mobility (CAM) services to be tested and evaluated, or they can bring equipment such as gateways to interconnect for example terrestrial and satellite systems, or for the maritime field trials, they can bring equipment for interference elimination during the communication between ferries. The usefulness of the external services/equipment will be evaluated by a group of partners participating in the project.

Another incentive for the external SMEs is to bring ideas and possible innovations on CAM services so that they can be tested in real field environments prior to be placed in the market. In order to facilitate this process, the project will construct a testbed which will be available for SMEs to foster rapid development and testing of new and innovative enablers and use cases that can possibly foster new products for future CAM services. This process will be done through 5G-ROUTES Open Calls, to be announced through the 5G-ROUTES web site, that will allow external SMEs to bring their CAM services to be tested on top of the 5G-ROUTES infrastructure.

The overall goal is to prepare the means of the Open Calls for inviting external SMEs to test CAM services and/or bring devices to the field trials for facilitating the experimental set-ups of the 5G-ROUTES infrastructure. In addition, the aim is to provide an information package that the external SMEs can evaluate and decide whether it is of their benefit to participate during the field trials for the purpose of advertising their CAM service, or equipment to a larger community.

The main work of this deliverable is to present the needs and benefits for SMEs to enter the process of applying to the 5G-ROUTES consortium for testing possible enablers, CAM services and/or devices during the field trials of the project.

Information regarding the 5G-architecture, use cases and enablers is provided to facilitate third-party SMEs to gain a better understanding about the project and judge whether or not there are benefits to join the trials.

The deliverable presents the work carried out so far which mainly concentrated on the first Open Call and getting to know other SME companies that could possibly bring their CAM services for testing on the 5G-ROUTES infrastructure. The benefit for them will be to have a visibility of their product/service to the relevant community. Plans for how to reach additional SME members besides the Open Calls is also presented. In addition, an information package that describes the objectives of the project and the use cases to be used during the field trials is prepared which it was requested at the mid-term review from the reviewers.

The first Open Call for SMEs to participate with CAM service or with equipment that can facilitate the experimental means of 5G-ROUTES use cases was announced on the 15th of March 2022 [1].

The second phase of the Open Call will be announced in 2023 once the place of the field trials is known and tentatively scheduled for December 2023. Then, the last Open Call will be announced close to April 2024, depending on the dates of the final field trials.

2 Introduction

The main scope of this deliverable is to

1. Firstly, provide information about the 5G-ROUTES project regarding its architecture, the field trial sites, and the CAM services to be tested by the project partners. This will give an understanding to the external SMEs about the 5G-ROUTES project and how well they fit to apply and participate during the field trials,
2. Secondly, to provide an information package to the third-party SMEs about the procedure of how to apply and decide if it is of their benefit to participate. 5G-ROUTES will announce three rounds of Open Calls to outreach external SMEs to join the project for the purpose to:
 - Improve the infrastructure with external means of equipment,
 - Bring advanced CAM use cases to be tested at the field trials,
 - Bring new enablers, use cases and technology at the field trials,
 - Support an innovative CAM cross corridor ecosystem around 5G-ROUTES,
 - Collect advanced and new market developments to improve technical capabilities missing from 5G-ROUTES.

All Open Call rounds will aim at finding innovative proposals that will enhance 5G-ROUTES objectives, provide advanced results, and bring new solutions for the cross-border corridors.

2.1 Mapping 5G-ROUTES Outputs

The purpose of this section is to map 5G-ROUTES's Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project's respective outputs and work performed.

Table 1: Adherence to 5G-ROUTES's GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

5G-ROUTES GA Component Title	5G-ROUTES GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
D6.5 Information package for external SMEs to facilitate the design of new CAM applications v1.0	<p>Actions and procedures undertaken for inviting SMEs to bring advanced CAM services and/or equipment to enhance 5G-ROUTES use cases that will all be tested at a cross-border environment.</p> <p>A report for consolidating the information package for the SMEs and procedures for evaluating the online application</p>	Chapter 3	<p>The information package for inviting external SMEs to design and test their CAM services is provided in chapter</p> <p>Error! Reference source not found.</p>
TASKS			

	<p>Identification of stakeholders in order to reach the most relevant SMEs and start-ups who are willing to contribute to the project with new components in order to address new CAM use cases. Definition of the objectives and guidelines, the terms and references of the selection procedure for the submission of their proposals and for their evaluation.</p>	<p>Chapter 0</p>	<p>Identification and analysis of the applications that will be from the Open Calls received by external SMEs who would like to contribute with new CAM services to the project. The winners will have to show validity and innovation of advanced CAM services and/or products that could facilitate 5G-ROUTES services at the cross-border ecosystem</p>
<p>T6.2 Engagement of external SMEs</p>	<p>In line with the stakeholders' engagement and community building strategy, this task will identify the right stakeholders in order to reach the most relevant SMEs and start-ups. This task will organize an invitation for third-parties (non-partners of the consortium: especially SMEs and spin-offs of research institutes) who are willing to contribute to the project with new components and CAM services during the field trials. After the external SMEs apply via an online application, the best ideas to exploit 5G-ROUTES results (Calls for Ideas) will be selected. The winners will be granted the right (prize) to participate to the 5G-ROUTES' booth in major 5G events (once a year), together with technical and business support from the main industrial partners of the</p>	<p>Chapter 3</p>	<p>The information package to third party SMEs is provided in chapter 3.</p>

	<p>project. This task aims at preparing the information package for the SMEs, managing the online application and the selection procedures for prizes, identifying the objectives and defining the guidelines, the terms and references of the selection procedure, for the submission of the proposals and for their evaluation</p>		
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2.2 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

The remainder of the document is structured as follows:

- Chapter 1 contains the executive summary of D6.5,
- Chapter **Error! Reference source not found.** highlights the chapters of this deliverable and its connection to other activities of the project,
- Chapter 3 describes the Information Package of 5G-ROUTES main aspects to the third-party SMEs including the objectives, overall concept, the 5G-ROUTES Use Cases, and the enablers including the 5G-ROUTES architecture, the use case and the enablers brought by the consortium to the project,
- Chapter 4 describes the identification of the SMEs, how they can participate in the project and the benefits they can gain from their participation in the 5G-ROUTES trials,
- Chapter 5 presents the topics of the Open Call, the requirements for the applicants to the Open Call, and the criteria and means of evaluation describes the means to advertise and publicize the Open Call to third-party SMEs so that the applicants know about the specific aspects of the Open Call and how they can participate in it,
- Chapter 6 describes the implementation package of the Open Calls,
- presents the actions that have been taken so far for the Open Call and plans for the future,
- Chapter 7 presents the KPIs for the SMEs who will test new CAM services and/or products,
- Chapter 8 concludes the deliverable.

2.3 Linkage to other Project Outputs

This section presents the relation and interdependencies of D6.5 with other deliverables of WP6 and with deliverables of other work-packages. The relation of this deliverable with other deliverables is presented in **Error! Reference source not found.** and described in **Error! Reference source not found.**. D6.5 is the deliverable that discusses aspects of the Open Call and how third-party applicants can bring CAM services and/or products to be tested on the 5G-ROUTES infrastructure.

As of this D6.5 will consider the results of previous work-packages of WP1 that discusses 5G-ROUTES CAM services and KPIs to be measured at the cross-border test sites,

- It will utilise the outputs of WP3 that describes the test site infrastructure,
- It will use the outputs of WP4 that describes in detail the CAM services that will be tested in the cross-border infrastructure,

- It will use the outputs of D6.1 and especially the channels and means provided in this deliverable for promoting the Open Calls, and lastly,
- It will provide input to D6.6 which will detail the final outcomes from the Open Calls.

Table 2: 5G-ROUTES deliverables related to D6.5

5G-ROUTES GA Component Title	Contribution and Value of linkage
INPUTS from other deliverables considered in this report	
D1.1 Use Cases, scenarios, specs & target KPIs for 5G for CAM	Linkage: Specifications and requirements of the Use Cases.
D1.9 Use Cases, scenarios, specs and target KPIs	Linkage: KPIs are selected for the use cases
D3.3 CAM infrastructure development	Enablers at cross border environments
D3.5 Integration of technological enablers with MNO 5G infrastructure	Incorporation of enablers in the 5G infrastructure of MNOs
D4.3 5G CAM field trials v1.0	Use cases
D6.1 Dissemination & Communication plans and activities	Describes the different channels that can be used for disseminating the package that is to be delivered to third-party SMEs.
OUTPUTS from this report used by other deliverables	
D6.6 Information package for external SMEs to facilitate the design of new CAM applications final version	All chapters

Figure 1: Relation of D6.5 to other deliverables

3 Information Package of 5G-ROUTES for third-party SMEs

3.1 Introduction to 5G-ROUTES

5G-ROUTES is an ICT-53 project whose main objective is to conduct advanced field trials of most representative and innovative CAM applications seamlessly functioning across a designated 5G cross-border corridor ('Via Baltica-North') spanning across 3 EU member states borders (Latvia-Estonia-Finland) in order to validate the latest 5G features and 3GPP specifications under realistic conditions, so as to **accelerate the widespread deployment** of 5G E2E interoperable CAM ecosystems and services in digitized motorways and shipways throughout Europe. The scope of this information package is to provide information to third-party SMEs about the project and specifically information regarding the field trials and the sites where the use cases will be executed. This will provide knowledge to the external SMEs to understand whether or not they should participate during the field trials. Other projects that have requested the participation of third-party SMEs at the field trials are: aeros project [1], the interconnect project[2], 5G-IANA project[3].

3.2 5G-ROUTES Objectives

- Objective 1: Development of innovative and commercially exploitable CAM use cases in cross-border environments for automotive and maritime sectors.
- Objective 2: Analysis of the technical and business requirements for the use cases to enable large-scale CAM field trials in the Via Baltica-North 5G corridor.
- Objective 3: Advancement and optimization of enabling technologies using AI for the reliable, seamless and uninterrupted delivery of interoperable CAM services across borders.
- Objective 4: Derivation of key assets from previous results and commercial products; to integrate the technological enablers in an end-to-end CAM ecosystem, to set up the 5G corridor and to facilitate lab and large-scale field trial validation.
- Objective 5: Demonstration of the potential and the user value in advanced CAM deployments at cross-border areas, by characterizing and optimizing 5G technologies at both lab tests and large-scale trials, to validate applicable standards and key target KPIs thus boosting the confidence for wide adoption of interoperable CAM services in Europe.
- Objective 6: Development and validation of business models of advanced CAM use cases that can be offered on top of existing services in a multi cross-border 5G operator environment, demonstrating benefits from potential operational cost reductions and new revenue generation streams. To protect EU IP and ensure long-term economic sustainability.
- Objective 7: Contribution to Standardization,
- Objective 8: Success through long-term dissemination of project's results.

3.3 Overall Concept of 5G-ROUTES

The 5G-ROUTES approach is structured in three pillars:

1. Formulation and validation of innovative use cases relevant to CAM services at cross-border across the 'Via Baltica-North' 5G corridor,
2. Developing advanced technological enablers for facilitating the execution of the field trials,
3. Aligning the implementation roadmap of 5G-ROUTES roadmap with the latest 3GPP standardization releases.

3.4 Field trial sites

The 5G-ROUTES project will utilize three trial sites where the use cases will be executed and tested. These sites can be used also by the third-party experimenters to bring their own use case and/or equipment to be tested

during the programmed trials. The three trial sites that will be used for the operation and testing of the use cases are described underneath:

1. Maritime ecosystem which is represented by the sea between the ports of Vuosaari at Helsinki and Muuga port at Tallinn and use cases that will operate during a ferry trip will be tested. In the following Figure 2, a picture of a ferry is shown as it departs from a port.

Figure 2: Ferry from Eckero line

2. Riga Bikiernieki racing track, in which site a virtual border is set-up by the mobile networks of Latvian Mobile Telecommunications (LMT) and Telia Estonia.
3. Valga (Estonia)/Valka (Latvia) site which is located at the border of Estonia and Latvia and be used for use cases dealing with automated driving as it is shown in the following

Figure 3.

Figure 3: Cross border between Latvia and Estonia on the E264 (in Google Map)

3.5 5G-ROUTES Project Architecture

The 5G-ROUTES architecture which is seen in the following Figure 4, consists of two different networks that belong to different administrative domains. In this figure the two domains are made at the border between Estonia and Latvia. The infrastructure consists of 5G New Radios and Standalone (SA) core network products from Ericsson with implementations of 3GPP Rel.15 and Rel.16 functionalities. It is based on the 3GPP service-based architecture that runs a framework where common applications are to be deployed using components with standard interfaces. The infrastructure is compatible with 3GPP VNFs and CNFs. The Radio Access Network (RAN) will be based on 5G NR gNBs operating on 3.5 GHz and/or 700 MHz bands. The gNBs are supplied by Ericsson. On the Estonian side, the Telia transmission network, acting as backhaul network, will connect the 5G NR RAN with the TTU (TalTech) 5G SA Core and on the other side the 5G RAN will be connected to the LMT 5G SA.

For the maritime, the architecture has not been finalized, but it will consist of two private networks installed in two ferries, a public 5G SA network at a shore and a satellite link connecting the ferries to the internet. The communication between the ferries and between a ferry and the public network is done with 5G NR base stations.

Figure 4: 5G-ROUTES terrestrial architecture

3.6 Innovative Use Cases to be tested in the field trials

The use cases that will be demonstrated and tested at the field trials are concentrated in two main ecosystems:

- **Maritime ecosystem**, in which the following use cases will be trialled:
 - UC5.1 focuses on connected logistics,
 - UC5.2 Live video streaming between ferries and between ferry and harbour at cross border,
 - UC 4.1 360° immersive multi-user gaming on the go

- **Terrestrial ecosystem**, consisting of the following use cases:
 - I. **See-through platooning**. This use case builds on UC1.1, UC1.2 and UC1.3.
 - II. **Sharing perception and road hazard at the border for connected and automated driving**. This use case builds on UC2.1, UC3.1 and a refocused UC3.3.
 - III. **Infotainment: Real-time virtual collaboration and gaming**.
 - UC4.1: 360° immersive multi-user gaming on the go
 - UC4.2: 3D Real-time virtual collaboration on the move

3.7 5G-ROUTES enablers

The aim of the 5G-ROUTES enablers is to enhance the performance of the use cases. These enablers can collaborate with external enablers brought by the third-party SMEs to provide improvement to the 5G-ROUTES use cases. These enablers are:

- CAM repository that manages and stores the artefacts required to instantiate the CAM services,
- Assisted Service Continuity for CAM Services that announces IP addresses of enablers and CAM services,
- Low-Latency Cross-Border Synchronization Mechanism for Seamless CAM Service Delivery that provides a low-latency mechanism when services are relocated at a cross administrative domain,
- Object Fusion for Improved Situational Awareness that assists in the provision of environmental perception to the road users,
- V2X Message Routing Via MEC that assists in the provision of message sharing to the road users,
- Predictive Resource Allocation of V2X related Network Functions that predicts movement at the cross-border and assists in the placement of the service in the two administrative domains, and
- The Tenant Web Portal for facilitating the parallel execution of the use cases, automate and accelerate the analysis, benchmarking and presentation of the results from the cross-border field trials, and the validation of key target KPIs as well as onboarding on network (CAM) services to the CAM repository.

4 Involvement and benefits of third-party SMEs to be involved in 5G-ROUTES

4.1 Who are the third-party SMEs

The SMEs that will apply as experimenters during the field trials are interested SMEs, start-ups, research Institutions that would like to boost their role in developing and/or testing use cases and equipment in realistic 5G scenarios. Their role will be to

- To leverage on an open platform their use case to be tested,
- To bring equipment to be integrated in the 5G-ROUTES architecture to boost the architecture functionality,
- To test and validate use cases, through 5G-ROUTES architecture,
- To utilize the available assets from the 5G-ROUTES trial sites.

4.2 Involvement of third-party SMEs

The involvement of third-party SMEs can be done via the 5G-ROUTES website. A detailed description of all assets in each field trial and maritime, resources provided by the project, expression of interest, eligibility criteria, funding/prizes are described in the 5G-ROUTES website and more information on these aspects is provided in the following chapter.

4.3 Benefits of SMEs from participating in the field and maritime trials

The third-party SMEs will gain from their participation in the 5G-ROUTES field trials by being exposed to a 5G infrastructure that can host their equipment for testing and an open platform that can host a service to be evaluated at the trial.

Also, the external SMEs can meet partners from the project with similar interest and expose and run their service/equipment to these partners.

5 Introduction to 5G-ROUTES Open Calls

5.1 Goals

5G-ROUTES will advocate its infrastructure to third-party SMEs that could join the project via Open Calls. The scope is to bring advanced use cases and/or equipment that can be used and tested during the field trials. The goals is to:

- Validate the 5G infrastructure at a cross-border corridor,
- Enhance the CAM services with new components that assist and improve the cross-border movement,
- To increase the visibility of 5G-ROUTES in the CAM community.

5.2 Challenges for third-party SMEs

The challenges for the Open Call applicants are:

- Design and integrate advanced components that can assist to improve the performance of the 5G-ROUTES use cases,
- Design, implementation and integration of CAM services that provide value to the 5G-ROUTES project,
- Integration of testing tools that will assist in the assessment of the performance of the network when the use cases operate,
- Design and integration of AI tools to advance 5G-ROUTES use cases.

5.3 Communication Strategy of Open Calls

The process of inviting external SMEs to join the 5G-ROUTES project is mainly based on the Open Call announcement, which is the main tool for promoting the invitation to the third-party SMEs. The Open Calls will be accompanied by other secondary efforts such as workshops, webinars etc. The communication strategy is based on three Open Calls as it is shown in the following Figure 5.

Figure 5: Communication strategy roadmap

The Open Call is based on presenting the 5G-ROUTES project with its upcoming results in the 5G-ROUTES website so that interested parties can apply and join the efforts of the consortium in presenting interesting results during the field trials. In addition, the site will provide:

- Video presentation of the project,
- Slide presentation of the project,

- Email address for questions and answers about the Open Call.

During the first Open Call there were two external SMEs that were interested in bringing their equipment to be used in collaboration with the CAM use case trials. The main business task of the interested companies were:

One company was the producer of 5G gateways able to provide connectivity during roaming at a cross-border. The second company was working on a V2X tele-operation use case. More information on the results of the 1st Open Call is provided in section 7.1.2. The 2nd Open Call will take place around December 2023 for inviting applicants to submit a proposal for participating at the second field trials and the third Open Call will be in May 2024 whose target will be to invite third-party SMEs to apply for participating at the final field trials.

5.4 Other Complimentary Communication Means

Besides the Open Call strategy, the project and the collaboration of external SMEs with 5G-ROUTES partners will be presented through webinars, workshops, to the 5G-CAM group etc. The purpose of these events is to let SMEs know that the 5G-ROUTES project is undertaking the task of field-testing CAM use cases at the 'Via Baltica' cross border at Valga-Valka cross-border. In addition, round tables at workshops can be organized where different ideas around testing CAM services at cross-border could be discussed. This is already done as it is described in more details in chapter **Error! Reference source not found.**

5.5 Eligibility criteria

The applicant needs to satisfy the following criteria:

- European SME, or start-up established in a legally eligible country. Eligible countries are the ones referred in the Horizon Europe rules [5],
- Proposal must be aligned to the objectives of 5G-ROUTES,
- Proposal must be written in English.

5.6 Funding/Prize

The selected external SMEs will be granted the right (prize) to participate in the 5G-ROUTES booth in major 5G events (once a year), together with technical and business support from the partners of the project. Additionally, the consortium will allocate a 20K€ additional funding for the participation of external SMEs in the field trials, which is under the final approval of the consortium by the time of updating this document.

5.7 Anticipated Gains of third-party SMEs by Participating in the Field Trials

However, the benefits from the participation of an external SME in the field trials can be:

- publicity and business value in the market,
- opportunity for testing a new CAM service and/or prototype equipment,
- opportunity to collaborate with partners and get to know each other for future synergies,
- test and validate a new service utilizing an established 5G infrastructure,
- explore new business models in 5G,
- gain visibility in EU level, 5G community and the automotive industry,
- access the CAM services platform to develop, deploy and test their services,
- accessibility to On Board Units (OBUs) and Road Side Units (RSUs) resources through the CAM services platform.

6 Implementation of Open Calls

6.1 Definition of the Open Call

This section defines the Open Call objective for bringing third-party SME companies to test their CAM services on the 5G-ROUTES field trials infrastructure.

Aim of the Open Call is to invite as many SMEs for CAM service collaboration and testing as possible. 5G-ROUTES consortium will enable testing by offering test environments and support for CAM testing. With this approach the consortium hopes to achieve new innovative CAM services, which could be linked to the test services of the 5G ROUTES project. In addition, this initiative will expand 5G and CAM service knowledge among the ITS industry.

6.2 Open Call topics which are related to testing new CAM services to 5G-ROUTES field trials

This section defines the topics and the possible CAM services that could be tested in the field trials. Testing must utilize 5G ROUTES field trial sites, but the focus area of the tests can be decided by the candidate.

Possible focus area examples:

- 5G CAM device testing:
 - A candidate can bring his/her own device and test it in the 5G-ROUTES infrastructure,
 - Currently test sites include the following devices:
 - OBUs:
 - RSUs:
- 5G CAM service testing:
 - A candidate can provide a CAM service to be tested at a field trial,
 - Current CAM service portfolio includes the following CAM services:
 - Dynamic vehicle platooning,
 - Cooperative lane change,
 - See through view for safe automated overtake,
 - Real time traffic information and cooperative intersection collision control,
 - Traffic jam chauffer,
 - Sensor info sharing for cooperative situation awareness,
 - VRU collision avoidance,
 - 360° immersive multi-user gaming on the go,
 - 3D real time virtual collaboration on the move,
 - Goods tracking visibility in multimodal cross border logistics,
 - Situational Awareness on Ferry, updated to video streaming between ferries.
- 5G CAM network/communication availability for testing CAM services:
 - Field trial ecosystems offer a fully functional 5G network which can be utilized for 5G CAM network testing,
 - 5G ROUTES trial sites can offer flexibility and adjustments from network side in close collaboration with MNOs to test external CAM services.

6.3 Requirements of the Open Call

This section defines the profile of the candidates and the requirements set by 5G-ROUTES consortium.

- Requirements on the profile of the external SME candidates:
 - candidate must be a legal entity
 - candidate must sign 5G ROUTES collaboration agreement

- candidate must follow and agree to the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity and 5G ROUTES ethics. Proposal has to be submitted in the 5G-ROUTES submission tool by using a specific template.

6.4 Preparation of a proposal and submission

The interested participant will need to prepare a proposal. The procedure is divided into three steps as explained below.

1. Section 1: Data about the applicant: entity name, entity type, company website,
2. Section 2: Information of the proposal: name, key challenges, main results to be achieved,
3. Section 3: Availability at the field trial, including information about agreement for the benefits of collaboration.

6.5 Submission phase

This section defines the submission tool that will be used for the applicants to prepare and upload the proposed CAM service. During this process there will be full support to questions that the applicants may have. The submission phase will include:

- Timeline of proposal's submission,
- Support means to the applicants. Can provide all equipment means and test support for the trial,
- Proposed days for the testing of the new CAM services.

Before the submission of the form, the applicant has to write a short proposal in pdf format of maximum 2 pages according to a template that will be provided on the website and is outlined below.

6.6 Template of the proposal

Applicants must prepare a written proposal with a maximum of 2 pages to be evaluated which will be the core material of their solution to be brought at the field trials. The Application Package will include:

1. **Administrative part:** this part includes general information about the profile of the applicant (company name, country,
2. **Proposal**
 - a) The proposal should contain the core idea of the CAM service or equipment to be tested at the cross-border,
 - b) Innovation of the service and/or the equipment,
 - c) Description of the results to be achieved.
3. **Relevance to 5G-ROUTES**
 - a) Description of how relevant the service or equipment is to the tasks and objective of 5G-ROUTES,
 - b) Explanation of the improvement that the brought solution could provide to 5G-ROUTES.
4. **Implementation means**
 - a) Roadmap of the work to be done,
 - b) Description of the necessary means required to integrate its service and/or equipment to the 5G-ROUTES infrastructure.

6.7 Evaluation of the applicants

This section defines the procedure of how to evaluate the submitted proposals. If the proposals are few. the evaluation procedure will go through a technical examination. The examination team will consist of the Technical Manager and the Task Leader of T6.2.

6.7.1 Evaluation procedure in case of few proposal submissions

When the number of proposals are a few below 5, then the evaluation committee will consist of the technical manager and the T6.2 leader. The evaluation criteria will be as:

- a) Proposal relevance to 5G-ROUTES objectives: 30%,
- b) Proposal innovation, (a new CAM service), to the project: 40%,
- c) Means of implementation at the field trials: 30%

6.7.2 Evaluation procedure in case of more than five submissions

When the number of submissions is more than five then the evaluation team will consist of the technical manager, the task leader T6.2, the WP3 leader and WP4 leader. The evaluation criteria will be as:

- a) Proposal relevance to 5G-ROUTES objectives:15%,
- b) Proposal innovation to the project: 40%,
- c) Means of implementation at the field trials: 15%,
- d) Impact to the market: 15%,
- e) Technical innovation: 15%.

7 First Open Call Implementation

The first Open Call was announced on the 15th of March 2022 [4]. Below the information that was provided on the 5G-Routes site as a snapshot of information to the applicants is provided.

7.1 First Open Call for SMEs, start-ups and spin-offs for CAM service testing

The first 5G-ROUTES Open Call was officially announced and started on the 15th of March 2022! The 5G-ROUTES project invited third-party SMEs and spin-offs to submit a draft proposal with regards to a CAM service they would like to bring for testing in one of the two cross corridor places of Bikiernecki or Valga-Valka in the border of Estonia-Latvia. The Open Call #1 started on March 15th of 2022 for testing CAM services in the period of May 1st – May 15th, 2022, and involved a 5G NSA infrastructure in the above places, while Open Call #2 will be announced shortly in 2023 when the 5G SA infrastructure is set-up and provided in the above places. The scope of both Open Call rounds aims to provide the 5G-ROUTES infrastructure for the interested external SME parties to bring short proposals describing their CAM services that will **enhance the 5G-ROUTES** test cases. Call proposals are expected to enhance the CAM services that will be tested by the 5G-ROUTES partners.

7.1.1 APPLICABILITY AND ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA

Only European SMEs, start-ups and research spin-offs were able to submit proposals:

Operational eligibility criteria for proposals were:

- Only one SME per proposal was admitted,
- The proposals should contribute to the extension of the 5G-ROUTES CAM services,

Administrative (and other) criteria are as follows:

- **Proposal** should be written in English in all their parts to be eligible,
- **Proposal** should be maximum one page long,
- **Prize:** local publicity and participation in a joint booth at a major 5G event,
- **Opening date:** 15.03.2022,
- **Closing date:** 20.04.2022,
- **Results announced:** 26.04.2022,
- **Contact person:** George Agapiou, David Pubill,
- **Email:** gagapiou@wings-ict-solutions.eu, david.pubill@cttc.cat,
- **Date for planned tests:** 01.05.2022 – 15.05.2022,
- **Project's web site:** <https://www.5g-routes.eu/>.

7.1.2 Results of the First Open Call

The outcome of the first Open Call was to receive two applications. These applications were:

- One interest was expressed from the SME company Goodmill Systems whose main contribution was to bring a router gateway that provides seamless connectivity in a cross-border. This gateway was equipped with double SIM card, and it was tested in a cross-border at Valga-Valka cross-border in a roaming situation and it was verified that it is functioning very well and could help 5G-ROUTES use cases during the field trials at cross-border.
- The second interest was expressed from the SME company GetUGo whose main interest was in bringing a tele-operation service to be tested. However, due to the fact that at Bikiernecki there was a simulated cross-border environment, this test was postponed for the future when tests will take place at a real cross-border at Valga-Valka.
- Additional interest arose recently from the Lithuanian logistics and transport sector with a number of interested third-party SMEs interested in joining the 5G-ROUTES project during the field trials.

7.1.3 Roadmap for coming Open Calls

According to Figure 5, the plan is to have an Open Call every time there is a field test for testing CAM services. The Open Call will be presented at the 5G-ROUTES site along with the information and application packages for possible external SMEs to present their interest and apply to participate in the testing phase. Two more Open Calls will be announced as soon as the dates of the field trials are set by the 5G-ROUTES management. The outcomes of all Open Calls will be assessed and presented at the upcoming deliverable D6.6 due month 44.

The roadmap of the upcoming calls is shown below in Table 3 and presented also in Figure 5.

Table 3: Roadmap for Open Calls

Open Call	Date	Place	Technology
2nd	December 2023	Valga - Valka	5G SA
third	April 2024	Valga – Valka, Maritime	5G SA with slicing support

8 Conclusions

The 5G-ROUTES project organized the first Open Call for inviting external to the project SMEs to test CAM services in the 5G-ROUTES infrastructure. The first Open Call brought the interest of two SME companies where one of them was suitable and selected to bring equipment to be tested at Bikierniecki site.

The first Open Call has shown that there is interest from external SMEs to come to the field trials with equipment and/or CAM service to participate at the testing phase. The first Open Call took place at Bikierniecki site which is a virtual cross-border, and this environment did not show a large interest from external SMEs.

An interest has been recently indicated from the Lithuanian Transport and Logistics sector to possibly bring some third-party SMEs to test use cases at the upcoming field and maritime trials.

The upcoming field trials will occur at Valga-Valka cross border which is a real cross border and thus more interested third-party SMEs are expected to apply. The same holds for the maritime ecosystem as external SMEs are expected to show interest to be involved in these trials. The Open Call includes information for the 5G-ROUTES project, it describes technical insights such as the project architecture, the enablers and the use cases that will be tested at the field trials, an Information Package for the applicants to decide whether or not they fit to participate, the prize for the involved external SMEs and as the project advances and comes close to real testing at terrestrial and maritime field trials the interest from external SMEs is expected to increase.

The roadmap for the upcoming Open Calls is shown in the following Figure 6. In December 2023 the second Open Call will be provided at the 5G-ROUTES website and the third one will be announced in April 2024 when the final field trials will take place.

Figure 6: Upcoming roadmap of Open Calls

Following the Open Calls, there will be an assessment of the Open Call announcements, and the procedure followed to attract the interest of external SMEs and how well the service and/or equipment brought by the applicant was performing.

With regards to the lessons learnt from the first Open Call, some hints have been followed by the T6.2 partners which are:

- Provide a better description of the objectives and challenges of the project,
- Provide more information for the 5G-ROUTES architecture and trial sites,
- Describe the information package and evaluation procedure for the applicants and present a prize,
- Publicize the Open Calls in a better way,

- Elaborate a better procedure for the evaluation of applicants,
- Describe the assets brought by the project and the benefits of the external SMEs by participating in the terrestrial and maritime trials,
- Specify better the criteria for the applicants.

References

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